

SOCIAL SCIENCES

SOCIAL WORKER IN SECONDARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN AZERBAIJAN: DEMAND AND NECESSITY

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Abstract

The presence of social workers in secondary schools plays an important role in improving the quality of education, maintaining internal discipline and developing social cooperation. The demand for social workers in secondary educational institutions in Azerbaijan is very high. Because social workers support students and their families to make the educational process more qualitative and effective, as well as help solve social problems and provide additional incentives for students' development. The activities of social workers help to make the educational environment more favorable by establishing healthy relationships between students, school and parents, and teachers and students. The article justifies the importance of social workers in secondary schools in Azerbaijan and mentions the work they will perform, their duties, and offers staff training in the specialty of "social worker working with secondary school students".

Keywords: *social worker, school, student, education, training, education, social development.*

Introduction. Social work is an assisting profession with the primary and fundamental goal of reasonably and comprehensively aiding individuals, groups, and communities in addressing and overcoming their intricate socio-economic and psychological challenges. Social workers apply their practice based on their own experiences and specialized education in social work. Social work is a professional service grounded in scientific knowledge and skills in human relations, designed to assist individuals, whether independently or in groups, in attaining social and personal satisfaction, as well as independence.

Research emphasizes that social work is a professional endeavor aimed at increasing or restoring the ability of individuals, groups, or communities to engage in social activities. Additionally, it is noted that social work involves professional activities directed towards enhancing or restoring the social functioning capabilities of individuals, groups, or communities and assisting in the creation of favorable social conditions for this purpose.

Social justice, human rights, collective responsibility, and respect for diversity are central principles of social work. Social workers have the capacity to engage individuals and structures to address life problems and enhance well-being. Grounded in research, policy, organization, intervention strategies, and their education, social workers undertake activities aimed at improving the behavior, relationships, quality of life, and well-being of individuals, families, groups, and communities. Oppenheimer notes that a crucial function of a school social worker is to identify and demonstrate necessary changes by substantiating adverse conditions that underlie the difficulties students face in school, thereby assisting in the reorganization of school leadership and experience (Lela Costin; 1995).

Towards the end of the 19th century and the early 20th century, social workers began operating in secondary education institutions in several countries. In Great Britain, this practice dates back to the late 19th century, in the United States to the early 20th century, in Canada from the 1940s, in Sweden, Finland, Norway, Denmark, and Iceland from the 1940s, in the Netherlands from the 1940s, in Malta from 1946, in Argentina from the 1960s, in Hong Kong from 1970, in the United Arab Emirates from 1972, and in Poland from 1975, social workers have been active in secondary schools (Huxtable, Marion, 2022).

Generally, over the last five decades, social work services have been established in secondary schools in Australia, South Korea, Japan, Norway, Austria, Switzerland, New Zealand, Russia, Latvia, Hungary, Lithuania, Estonia, Saudi Arabia, Luxembourg, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, and Mongolia (Huxtable, Marion, 2022).

Social worker in secondary school: emergence and activity

Social workers began working in Canadian schools in the late 1800s in Toronto, when disciplinary officers were hired to make sure children attended school (Grande et McClare, 1983). In 1919, the term was changed to attendance supervisors (Martelli, 1988). School social worker positions began to appear in the 1940s and 1950s (Loughborough, 2000). It should be noted that the duties of attendance supervisors and school social workers are closely related. In many Canadian school boards, the social worker continues to be responsible for school attendance issues. It is estimated that there are currently approximately 750 school social workers in Canada (Loughborough, 2000).

In 1982, the Canadian Association of Social Workers and School Attendance Counselors (CASSWAC) was established in Western Canada. The

mandate of this organization is to promote the development of quality social work and counseling services related to school attendance in Canada. CASSWAC is a national association of school social workers.

The International Network of School Social Workers was established in 1990 by the Arizona School Social Work Association (School Social Work Association of America (SSWAA), 2001). This network contains information about school social services in 26 countries, including Canada.

School social workers provide unique services to students, families, schools, and communities to help students get the most out of school programs (CASSWAC, 2001).

School social workers provide the following services to students experiencing difficulties at school:

- advisory services for school leaders, teachers, support staff and parents;
- individual counseling and student support services;
- family counseling and support services for parents;
- group counseling services for students;
- educational programs and presentations for parents and school staff;
- communication services between parents and school;
- referral services to community organizations;
- community development programs;
- collaborative services with community programs (CASSWAC, 2001);
- other special services to meet the special needs of students.

School social workers with a professional degree in social work often collaborate with teachers and health and psychological service professionals. School social workers determine whether problems related to student attendance, academic indifference, aggressive behavior originate from the family or are related to peers. Although the school social worker is expected to do most of her work within the school, she may work with other school staff to conduct assessments and counseling in students' homes.

Thus, school social workers help students who have problems at school, at home and in the community. Recognizing that the environment is both distinct from and related to home and family life, school social workers work directly with children, adolescents, parents, teachers and other school staff (Le travailleur social en milieu scolaire, 2002).

Working as part of a local team of teachers and other school staff, school social workers help students in a variety of ways. While the primary responsibility for instruction rests with teachers and administrators, social workers help students with learning difficulties, respect for peers, peer relationships, sexuality, delinquency, and conflict resolution with parents.

Because the school social worker understands the psychosocial factors that promote optimal learning, their job is to help children stay in school and learn well (International Network of School Social Workers, 2001). To do this, it may also take on a leadership role within the school district or community to encourage

the creation or implementation of social service programs (Ordre professionnel des travailleurs sociaux du Québec [OPTSQ], 1997).

Social workers can also assess behaviors related to physical, sexual, and emotional abuse or substance abuse and make referrals to child welfare agencies, doctors, and psychologists. Although counseling begins with the child, depending on the nature of the problem, other services may be called upon to protect and promote the child's personal, academic, and social development.

The Code of Ethics (ACTS, 1994) defines the basic principles of social work practice. Because the majority of students are under 16 years of age, prior to providing services, the social worker must obtain consent from the parent or guardian, as well as from the child, to respect confidentiality parameters between them. Whether or not there is consent, child protection authorities must be informed of suspected or discovered cases of child abuse. In this case, school social workers can assist child welfare agencies in supporting the student and can bring the child's friends, family, school, and other resources from the community to the child's defense.

School social workers are also concerned with special needs arising from physical or mental disabilities of children. Working closely with support resources and parents, teachers strive to recognize a child's strengths despite challenges that make learning or appropriate behavior difficult in the school environment. They teach sensitivity to other students and staff at school because they know the stresses that a child who is different from the majority of their peers in terms of language, race, culture, or socioeconomics can experience. It is sensitive care to the individual needs and problems of students and their families. In addition, they promote acceptance and tolerance and model these behaviors.

School social workers work to prevent crises large and small by developing or implementing programs that promote tolerance of differences. Although this proactive approach is largely effective, there remain cases where the specific training that social workers receive to address post-traumatic situations or direct objectification is used and valued. School social workers are at the forefront of identifying mental health problems and behaviors that pose a threat to the self or others, and to address the effects of crisis, community or social trauma spilling over into the classroom (Le travailleur social en milieu scolaire, 2002).

People who can benefit from the services of school social workers are:

- elementary school students who have difficulty in transitioning to secondary school;
- students with developmental delay affecting school activities;
- students experiencing trauma (for example, moving from another country, changing school, changing family composition, divorce, remarriage, death, etc.);
- students experiencing social or emotional behavioral difficulties at school, home or community;
- students who have difficulties in family life;

- students with substance addiction problems;
- students who are pregnant or become parents;
- students at risk of dropping out of school;
- students with learning difficulties or disabilities;
- students with poor school attendance (CASSWAC, 2001).

According to the International Network of School Social Workers, school social workers can perform the following tasks:

- Act as an advocate for clients, school social workers and the social work profession in general.
- Publish documents for parents and professionals.
- To conduct research in the field of social work in schools.
- Write, contribute and coordinate publication of materials for local school systems.
- Liaise with government agencies responsible for education, community and social services.
- Connecting with international, national, state school social worker organizations and practitioners (International Network of School Social Workers, 2001).

As in Canada, in Switzerland, there is a need to introduce social workers in secondary schools and define their responsibilities. Thus, compulsory schools in the country have registered an increase and complexity in the personal, social and educational problems of young people (truancy, family problems, school violence, etc.) during the last decades (Bohrer, 2009). This development has created an increasing need for educational and social support to support students in the face of everyday challenges in and out of school. In order to respond to this challenge and fulfill the school's mission of knowledge transfer, socialization and integration of children and youth, educational institutions have introduced social work into the school environment since the 1990s.

This innovation is part of a general trend in the organization of educational work, reflected in the strong growth of non-pedagogical education workers (educational consultants, educational assistants, etc.) in French schools since the 1980s (Van Zanten, 2012). This trend has since taken place in North American schools (Tardif & Levasseur, 2010). In the last decade, social work in schools has been firmly established in Swiss compulsory schools, mainly in orientation period institutions and some elementary schools, which are facing socially difficult situations.

Since 2010, the Department of Education and Cultural Affairs (DFAC) in the bilingual (French and German) Swiss canton of Fribourg, in cooperation with the municipalities, has developed the positions of social workers in schools, mainly in the German-speaking part. In French-speaking schools, where their presence is less common, social workers are entrenched in a field previously occupied by school mediators (Von Aarburg, 2014). Municipalities initially had a great deal of freedom in defining the missions and framework conditions of social workers in schools.

Subsequently, the inclusion of social work in schools in the new law on compulsory education (LS,

2014) and its implementing regulations (RLS, 2016) led to the adaptation of its administrative organization: this service is now part of the support system. School social workers are cited as a good decision that schools can benefit from in order to develop, maintain a quality school environment and care for students with behavioral problems.

The Swiss Social Work Professional Association has called for the following missions of social work in schools according to the cantonal official characteristics (AvenirSocial, 2016):

1. to support school principals who are responsible for developing and maintaining a quality school climate;
2. prevent social or behavioral problems, detect them early and develop social-educational care and treatment methods;
3. to implement this mandate at the level of all school stakeholders (students, teachers, management, parents, etc.);
4. to cooperate with other people in the school, authorities and internal services (school mediation, speech therapy services, psychology, etc.) or external (police, children and youth services, child psychiatric center, etc.) if necessary.

The above provides an idea of how social work practice can be applied in a school context. A school social worker who adheres to a belief system devoid of value judgments that values and respects the individual in his or her context faces unique challenges in the environment in which he or she works. By being both a member of the system and an intermediary for the system, he can make a valuable contribution to the lives of students and families, as well as schools and communities.

Benefits of social work in secondary school

Secondary school social work is a social-educational service that supports children and young people with everyday problems that may arise in and around the school. In collaboration with faculty, students, and families, the school social worker responds to academic, family, or psychosocial issues in a global context. School social work plays a preventive role, especially in terms of early detection of problems in educational institutions. The school social work service helps to mobilize the resources and skills of all stakeholders: students, teachers, parents, other stakeholders. This allows for coordinated working, promotes teaching and learning as a whole and supports the student's learning process.

School social work provides information, advice, support and monitoring to students and families. It is the link between the school and the young person's living environment and external structures. Also acts as a mediator between students and their environment (parents and school) in situations of violence and harassment and actively participates in creating a peaceful school environment with the entire educational community. He works by providing individual (interviews, home visits, etc.) or collective support to students while observing professional secrecy. At the same time, in close cooperation with members of the educational

community, he communicates with parents and participates in various internal and external commissions in the institution.

The following are the goals of social work in schools:

- To support and accompany children and young people in their education and social integration;
- To promote the quality of the school climate;
- To mobilize parent and family skills;
- To support the educational and training mandate of the school;
- Cooperate with stakeholders;
- To support the correct socialization of students;

The target audience of social work in secondary schools is students with primary, incomplete secondary and secondary education.

It is considered important to establish cooperation with the following actors for the implementation of social work in secondary schools:

- parents and referrals;
- teachers, school principals, employees of educational or non-school institutions;
- specialized services and authorities.

Theoretical approaches and intervention methods of social work in schools also differ. The school social worker is selected for his ease of access to management and other relevant official government agencies and his proximity to stakeholders. School social work bases its activities on the respect and promotion of children's rights, in particular the best interests of the child, the right to participation and non-discrimination. Social work in schools is based on theoretical and practical approaches in the professional field of social work. These provide a basis for defining the role and mandate of school social work and provide general guidelines for its job description. The methods of intervention are as follows:

- systematic approach;
- skills-based approach;
- a solution-oriented approach;
- conflict management, mediation;
- intervention and control;
- scientific research in the field of school social work.

Social work professionals in schools have a duty to respect their discretion and official confidentiality. As a reliable person, they should treat the received information with caution. If there is no other way out, they can transfer the information to third parties so that the directly concerned persons are informed and appropriate measures are taken to prevent possible threats. When students endanger themselves or others, school social workers have a responsibility to report the situation to the appropriate youth protection services. In this context, the child's interests are always the main decision criterion.

Records held by social work services are subject to data protection law and are sensitive information and confidential.

School social work is obliged to cooperate with all stakeholders of the school on an equal basis. Regardless of the teaching staff, the school social work is a neutral

body and promotes a relationship of trust between the student and the school social worker. Social work in schools may be subordinated to an organization outside the educational institution (for example, municipal or district social services, youth protection agency, counseling and assistance center for youth and families, etc.). Of course, this education depends on the management system and ways to protect the independence and increase the effectiveness of social work.

The beneficial effects of a social worker in high school. The employment of social workers in high schools can contribute to various beneficial effects in the field of education:

1. Support for the social and psychological development of students: Social workers provide support for students' social and psychological development, fostering their relationships with small groups, school communities, and families.

2. Enhancing students' responsibility and confidence: Social workers engage with students to develop leadership skills, problem-solving abilities, responsibility, and confidence.

3. Resolution of difficulties: They assist in resolving problems, misunderstandings, and difficulties among students, contributing to more effective outcomes in the learning process.

4. Collaboration with families: Social workers establish connections with students' families, creating a broader support network for students both at home and in school.

5. Support for group activities: They organize group activities to enhance students' social skills and provide support for the development of their cooperative abilities.

6. Treatment of psychological issues: Social workers help students address psychological issues and develop tailored support plans based on their needs.

7. Academic performance: When students' well-being and support are enhanced, their academic performance will also improve. Social workers will contribute to the success of students by solving the difficulties they face in their educational life.

8. Behavioral problems: Social workers will identify behavioral problems among students and offer early intervention and solutions. This will create peace and harmony in the school.

The presence of social workers in schools can bring about a more genuine and developed educational environment. This contributes to improving the learning process and helps enhance students' social and psychological well-being (David Dupper, 2003).

A social worker in schools: what does he do?

Social workers work with students, families, school staff, and communities to help students optimize their learning, success, and well-being. They understand the many factors that influence a student's life and behavior. They work with students to promote academic success and social adjustment.

Social workers in this field can help students deal with issues such as learning difficulties, peer pressure, peer relationships, sexuality, conflicts with the law, substance abuse, and conflicts with parents. They can

also plan events and activities to celebrate cultural diversity and promote cultural awareness among students, staff, and families.

"Data protection in social work - Practical help for managing sensitive personal data" published by the Swiss Professional Association for Social Work states that social workers respect diversity and different ways of accessing knowledge. They create an inclusive and safe environment for students, families and staff (AvenirSocial, 2014).

Social workers help students develop resilience, confidence, and self-efficacy. They believe that every student is an individual capable of learning, developing and solving problems (AvenirSocial, 2010). Social workers develop students' talents. To do this, they work closely with students, teachers, families and health professionals. They support students in achieving their goals and help remove barriers to education so that students can realize their potential.

School social workers can have a wide variety of roles:

- to give individual advice and support to students;
- counseling families and supporting caregivers;
- organizing support groups for students;
- providing support to students and employees after a traumatic event;
- prepare and provide training for childcare workers, families and staff;
- create open communication between students, families and school;
- refer students, educators and families to community organizations and other supports;
- planning and organizing special events for students, families and staff;
- develop and deliver community programs;
- defend the interests of students, schools and society when necessary.

Since social work is a field with an important role in education, social workers actively work to organize and create communication between teachers, students and families. They can support students' development by assessing their social and psychological needs and developing problem solving plans.

Social workers should also collaborate with community groups and organizations to help create appropriate supports and opportunities for students. By setting a position, they should work to improve relations between students and reach the maximum potential of each student.

School social workers support the social and psychological development of students, help solve their problems, and help create a safe and friendly environment for the school community. Social workers manage to increase care and attachment among students and help to make the educational process in the school more effective, in accordance with the needs and wishes of the community. School social workers work with the entire school on policies and educational programs, such as efforts to make schools safe for everyone. (Carol Rippey Massat, 2009)

Social workers help to change students' behavior in a positive way by applying individual or group

"treatment" strategies for educational deficits and problems. This ensures that students feel comfortable and safe in their learning environment and achieve better results. They also use their thinking to explore emotional, physical, and economic issues when solving a problem (School Social Work Guide, 2024).

The activity of social workers in the field of education is an effective approach to increase the social and academic achievements of students. Because the process is performed by an independent person who is not a party, professionals with psychological and social skills.

The difference between a secondary school social worker and other social workers is as follows:

1. Working in the educational environment: Secondary school social workers work primarily in the school environment and meet the needs of students. Other social workers may work in a variety of settings (hospitals, government agencies, community services, etc.).

2. Working with students: School social workers are primarily concerned with the emotional and psychological needs of students, as well as helping with their academic success and social development.

3. Cooperation with families and teachers: Social workers in secondary schools work closely with parents and teachers of students and work together to solve their problems.

4. Compliance with school rules: School social workers work in accordance with school rules and help regulate student behavior in accordance with school rules.

5. Meeting special needs: School social workers develop and implement special plans to support students with special needs.

To address the wide range of issues in the high school environment, school social workers must be able to assume a range of roles such as researcher, advocate, counselor, educator, publicist, speaker, and community organizer.

Duties of a secondary school social worker

The work of the social worker is more specifically aimed at creating favorable conditions for the prevention, promotion, screening and intervention of students and groups experiencing or likely to experience emotional, social, academic or family difficulties.

The social worker assists in the screening and identification of students with difficulties for the purpose of prevention and intervention; it assesses students with social, family, personal, or academic difficulties by studying and synthesizing data collected through direct observation or interviews, counseling, and surveys. At the same time, she/he conducts psychosocial assessments. Oversees the preparation and determination of a psychosocial treatment plan, its implementation, and provides psychosocial monitoring of the student.

The school social worker participates with a multidisciplinary team in developing, implementing, and revising a student intervention plan that takes into account personal, family, school, and social contexts to address student challenges and maintain and develop academic motivation. She/he collaborates with other

members of the team in consulting and coordinating interventions and evaluating the achievement of goals.

She/he conducts student and group meetings and individual support contact meetings, oversees support contact with parents. It directs the student or their parents to resources appropriate to the situation and needs. Cooperates with representatives of partner organizations.

The school social worker provides advice and support to teachers and other school stakeholders to better meet the needs of the student and ensure their academic support to continue their progress and success.

He participates in the development, promotion and implementation of screening, education and prevention programs on issues related to problems experienced by young people.

He advises the board, writes expert reports, evaluation reports and progress reports and makes relevant recommendations to support decision-making.

In addition, he may be called upon to intervene in crisis or emergency situations and suggest possible solutions.

The school social worker also prepares and updates files according to professional standards and established guidelines. Writes progress notes or milestone assessment reports, process completion and monitoring interventions.

The necessity of social work activity in secondary schools in Azerbaijan

The development of society and widespread use of the latest technologies have significantly influenced human relationships. Currently, the existing situation in secondary education institutions in our country (interactions among students, relationships with teachers, approaches to education, attitudes toward rules and discipline, etc.) does not fully align with the expectations of society. There is not a comprehensive understanding between schools, parents, and students. Each party has grievances and accusations sufficiently grounded and argued. It should be noted that recently there has been an increase in complaints about the rules of behavior of students in schools. It is an undeniable fact that there are children whom even teachers cannot cope with (Pia.az, 2023). Everyone wants a complex solution to the problem and places responsibility on the other party. Although these problems have been a subject of discussion for a long time, no solution has been found. It seems that, for this reason, parallel tutoring activities are developing alongside secondary education. We observe the informal withdrawal of secondary education from schools, and this must be acknowledged. Along with this, the environment necessary for the socialization of students, social education, moral values, national and spiritual values, etc., is lacking.

Lately, secondary schools in Azerbaijan often come up with negative topics, including the shameful situation in teacher-student relations. This causes serious dissatisfaction and concern of the society and opens the way for serious questions. In the recent videos from schools, one of the notable points is the increase in tendency towards the criminal world among high school students, and the rise in interest in criminal elements. In the videos, we observe that the names of criminal

authorities are written on the students' desks in the high school, students try to recreate them in separate episodes, and they show a tendency towards criminal elements (tehsilforumu.az, 2022).

Some negative situation that happens at school and even in society is sometimes immediately exaggerated and generalized against the background of the teacher's personality as a whole. If the name of the school, the teacher, is involved in local scandals, it does not bode well not only for the development of education, but also for the society as a whole. Therefore, it is necessary to think about the causes, not the results. As long as it is preferred to make decisions based on the result rather than the cause, there will be more unpleasant situations in schools that will surprise us. Let's not forget the fact that school is a part of society. The processes taking place in the society cannot fail to affect the school and the teacher. We need to agree that in our time, educational issues have not completely lost their former essence, value and relevance, but they tend to lose them and are very close to it.

However, no matter how many different instructions, methodical recommendations, regulations and other guiding normative documents there are on the organization of training and education in schools, attention to its content and essence has become one of the declining moral values. The quality of education has decreased. One of the main reasons is that the virtual space surpasses the live communication. From this point of view, approaching the issue from a purely pedagogical aspect and connecting it directly with the current state of education would be nothing but a one-sided approach to the issue.

If we take into account that training and upbringing as a social element is conditioned by other top institutions and basic elements of society, we can say that existing moral qualities do not affect the process of training and education of social, economic and legal relations etc. Therefore, the approach to what is happening must change. "Punishing the teacher is not a way out of the situation. How many teachers and heads of educational institutions have received various punishments in connection with such cases, and what has changed? On the contrary, the situation has become more tense and has become massive" (tehsilforumu.az, 2022).

While the implementation of interconnected works for solving the problem is essential, here, a specific proposal is suggested. It is the creation of the "social worker" position in secondary education institutions. As evident from the explanations and scientific foundations above, social workers will play a crucial role in schools. They have the potential to eliminate several reasons that create dissatisfaction in the country's society today.

In our opinion, the presence of social workers in Azerbaijani schools is necessary for several fundamental reasons:

1. Social workers provide psychological support to students. The presence of social workers in schools is imperative for finding the most professional solutions to issues and developing an action plan to ensure

the continuation of the success of our country in education for the bright future figures of tomorrow. This will help students focus more on their education.

2. Social workers offer various educational and developmental opportunities to students. In this regard, social workers in our country will encourage students to develop their skills and engage in independent activities.

3. School social workers will assist in developing students' social relationships with each other and with teachers. This contributes to enhancing students' social skills. In this context, not only development programs but also specialist support will play a significant role in increasing the social activity of Azerbaijani youth.

Apart from all these, the introduction of social workers in secondary schools can have a number of positive effects, such as:

1. More attention can be paid to the social and psychological needs of students, which can help meet the needs of students.

2. There may be certain problems and difficulties among the students, for example, behavioral problems or students who need support can be identified and provided with the necessary support.

3. If students need additional support for their academic and social development, this need can be identified and provided. This can create positive changes in the education system.

Thus, the presence of social workers in secondary schools seems to be an important step to more effectively support the needs and potential of students.

Therefore, the presence of social workers in Azerbaijani schools is crucial for the development of students and the enhancement of social well-being.

Preparation of social workers for middle schools in Azerbaijan

It is necessary for social workers to operate in schools to quickly address the problems of young people who are the founders of the future. To train social workers, they need to undergo various training programs and be able to integrate theory and practice. Understanding developmental theories is crucial for a school social worker because behaviors that may seem normal in a student's life can be considered regression or abnormal at other developmental stages. Therefore, a school social worker should adopt a specialized training program.

For the preparation of social workers working in schools in Azerbaijan, the following steps can be suggested:

1. Legislation and regulation development: Legislation and regulation should be developed and implemented to support the work of social workers in secondary schools.

2. Education and Experience: Schools should be staffed with social workers who have received the required education and gained experience in the field. Therefore, specialized training for the profession of "school social worker for middle school students" should be initiated at the bachelor's and master's levels. Through experience programs and relevant courses, the

skills and knowledge of social workers should be continually enhanced. They should learn the most optimal ways to handle various situations.

3. Assignment of social workers to schools: At least one social worker should be assigned to each secondary school. This is important to adequately respond to the needs of students. First of all, this process should be started from schools located in larger cities. Nowadays, social workers are not so needed in rural schools.

4. Education of school personnel: School personnel should be informed about the role of social workers and the work to be done in the school. This will increase cooperation and coordination with social workers.

5. Specific Professional Development Training: Specific and professional development training should be organized for social workers working in schools. These training programs will equip them with new skills to better respond to the evolving social needs of students, families, and the community.

6. Work Experience Programs: Work experience programs should be established in schools for the training of social workers. These programs provide an opportunity to work with school communities and gain experience in addressing the social and psychological needs of students.

7. Adaptation Programs with Mentorship: Establishing mentorship programs for new social workers in schools is beneficial. Experienced social workers can guide newcomers, helping them adapt more easily to the school working environment.

8. Core Professional Standards: Approved core professional standards and codes by professional organizations and education ministries should be applied. These standards help social workers adhere to professional ethics and understand their responsibilities.

9. Provision of resources: In order for social workers to function effectively, they must be provided with the necessary resources (workplace equipment, finance, information, etc.).

10. Cooperation with social workers: Cooperation between social workers and local executive authorities, parents, teachers and other relevant institutions should be increased.

11. Monitoring and evaluation: Regular monitoring should be done to assess the quality of social workers' performance and to make improvements in the necessary areas.

12. Counseling services for social workers: Professional counseling services should be provided for social workers to reduce their workload and improve the quality of work.

13. Public awareness: The public should be informed about the role and importance of social workers in schools so that their activities can be better supported.

Implementing these measures can provide a strong assurance for the education and training of social workers working in schools, contributing to a more effective and professional development in the social field.

The attitude of public opinion to the issue of social workers in secondary schools in Azerbaijan

Social workers in secondary schools in countries around the world pay attention to the social and psychological needs of students and help solve certain problems. This helps the academic and social development of students. However, social workers do not work in secondary schools in Azerbaijan. However, in addition to the theoretical justification of what kind of changes the activity of social workers in secondary

schools can create in Azerbaijan, there is a need to study the practical requirements for it. To clarify this, a survey was conducted among 100 people. The social status of the respondents who took part in the survey was as follows: 50% of the respondents were students, 13.2% were university students, 10.5% were teachers, 26.3% were parents.

The first question was devoted to studying the opinions of the respondents regarding whether there are gaps in the good education and upbringing of students in secondary schools. It is no coincidence that 67.3% of respondents indicated that there are gaps, and 32.5% of

respondents expressed their satisfaction with the current situation. Considering the opinions, it is noticeable that there are gaps, and their elimination is an urgent issue in the current scientific information society. (Figure 1.)

Figure 1.

The second question was: "Is there a need for social workers in secondary schools?". Although 81.6%

of the survey participants indicated that it was necessary, 18.4% stated that it was not necessary. The posi-

tive responses of the majority of respondents are interesting. It turns out that everyone is waiting for the solution of the problems in secondary schools. It seems that 18.4% of respondents did not see the need for the

role of social workers in this sector because the rights and duties of social workers are not clearly understood among the population. (Figure 2.)

Figure 2.

The third question was asked to determine what problems social workers can help with in secondary schools. According to survey results, 23.1% answered psychological problems, 25.6% social problems, 17.9% education, 23.1% nurture, 10.3% other problems.

From the answers of the respondents, it can be concluded that the population thinks that the activity of social workers in secondary schools will create a positive change in only part of the students' lives. Only 10.3% of respondents were able to correctly assess the role of social workers. (Figure 3.)

Figure 3.

The fourth question was about how important the guidance and support of social workers are for students in secondary school. 53.8% of respondents indicated that it is very important, 25.6% that it is important, 12.8% that it is moderately important, 2.6% that it is of little importance, and 5.1% that it is not important at all.

However, it is not so difficult to imagine that if social workers work in secondary schools, the problems faced by students in the family and at school will be revealed and the adaptation of students to the field of education will be carried out at a high level. (Figure 4.)

Figure 4.

The fifth question was "Can social workers provide emotional and mental support to students?". 76.3% of the respondents answered positively and 23.7% answered negatively. This shows that the majority of the

population supports the activity of social workers in secondary schools. (Figure 5).

Figure 5.

The sixth question is dedicated to clarifying the issue of how to make the activities of social workers more effective for students in secondary schools. 44.7% of the respondents recorded their answers through training, more than half of the respondents (52.6%) through interactive discussions, and only 2.6%

through other methods. Thus, there is a need to convey the role of social workers in society, as well as the positive change they can create in school, to the population through various discussions and awareness training. (Figure 6).

Figure 6.

The seventh question was formulated regarding the effects that social workers can have in the lives of students in secondary schools. Most of the survey participants (89.5%) said it would have a positive effect,

and 10.5% said it would not have any effect. It is a positive thing that no respondent mentioned that social workers will have a negative impact on students' lives. (Figure 7).

Figure 7.

The eighth question was: "How do you think it will affect the education system if specialized social workers work in secondary schools in Azerbaijan?" The answers given by the respondents to this question were in the form of positive, substantial, medium level,

normal influence. 80% of respondents said positively, 10% said it would lead to the social and psychological development of students, and 10% said it would not affect it. Some of the respondents mentioned that it can be very useful for students' socialization. (Figure 8.)

Figure 8

The ninth question was "If specialized social workers work in secondary schools in Azerbaijan, how will this affect the students?" Most of the answers to this question are positive. Most of the respondents came to the conclusion that social workers will be engaged in training and education of students. Thus, 55%

of the respondents indicated that it would have a very positive effect, 25% of the respondents indicated that it had an average effect, and 20% of the respondents indicated that it had a bad effect. (Figure 9.)

Figure 9.

The tenth question of the survey was about what kind of work social workers do in secondary schools. And based on the answers, the respondents mentioned that in addition to education, especially, social workers should deal with issues such as psychological issues,

social issues, and rule-making. 50% of survey participants emphasized that social workers are expected to deal with education, 30% with upbringing, and 20% with social psychological issues in high school. (Figure 10.)

Figure 10.

The eleventh question is as follows: "Do you think that if specialized social workers work in secondary schools in Azerbaijan, it will have a better effect on the upbringing or education of students?" 26.3% of respondents said it will affect their upbringing, 26.3%

their education, and 47.4% said it would affect both. Thus, the respondents noted that social workers will have a positive effect on the education and upbringing of students. (Figure 11.)

Figure 11.

Based on the analysis of the survey results, it is possible to observe that the population wants social workers to work in secondary schools of Azerbaijan. The analysis of this survey produced the following main results:

1. The need for the support of social workers: The population supports the activity of social workers in secondary schools, thinking that it will have a positive effect on education, upbringing and the development of students. The involvement of social workers can positively impact students' emotional and psychological well-being, academic success, and overall school environment.

2. Lack of information: It turns out that some people participating in the survey do not have enough information about the duties and functions of social workers. This lack of information highlights the importance of educating the public to better understand the role of social workers and better benefit from their services.

3. Limits of public expectations of social workers: The public recognizes that social workers are important for the well-being, safety and development of students in schools. At the same time, social workers cooperate with parents to better understand the needs of students and solve their problems.

4. The need for social workers' services: The survey results highlight the importance of strengthening

the role of social workers in secondary schools. The public wants more social workers in schools and better access to their services.

Referring to these results, it is possible to recommend the strengthening of the role of social workers in the education system, in particular, the creation of a staff unit of social workers in secondary schools, steps to inform the population and increase the quality of social services.

Conclusion

When discussing the improvement of the quality of education in our country's secondary schools in the modern era, many focus on training outcomes, content standards, and teaching strategies. However, the issue lies in the fact that schools cannot convince students of the necessity of gathering in classrooms to apply these principles and provide them with education. Even parents approach this with skepticism. Therefore, we observe various approaches in secondary education institutions, teachers, school directors, such as diagnostic assessments of teachers, exams, interviews with directors, and school management issues. Of course, the main goal in all of this is to raise the quality of education, consisting of raising the intellectual level, developing an scientific worldview, promoting independent thinking, and fostering creative activities in the young generation, who are the future builders of our country. This should be appreciated in its own right.

However, the fundamental issue is the formation of a teaching and learning environment in secondary schools and the establishment of a system of proper and clear relationships. It is impossible to achieve positive success in an environment where there is a lack of trust in the school, students who do not want to learn from teachers, and parents who do not believe in the school. To solve all these problems, as seen in many countries worldwide, there is a need for active involvement of social workers in secondary schools in Azerbaijan. Only the intervention of a social worker can eliminate these problems. Social workers can organize communication and create a cooperative environment between teachers, students, and families. They can contribute to improving relationships among students and increasing their social and academic achievements. To address the broad spectrum of problems in secondary schools, school social workers can take on various roles such as researcher, advocate, consultant, educator, community organizer, speaker, and organizational facilitator. This requires a comprehensive approach to problem-solving and the practical implementation of educational reforms in practice.

Thus, the necessity of appointing the position of a social worker in secondary schools and the commencement of the activities of social workers is evident. For this purpose, specialists with the specialization of "school social worker for middle school students" are required, and it is possible to implement this training at the bachelor's and master's levels.

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